

ASSESSMENT OF PATIENT SATISFACTION FOR THE AVAILABILITY OF BEDS AND OTHER OUTFLOW MEASURES IMPLEMENTED TO REDUCE OVERCROWDING IN THE EMERGENCY AND TRAUMA DEPARTMENT OF A RURAL GOVERNMENT HOSPITAL IN UTTAR PRADESH, INDIA

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Abstract

Background: One frequent issue that frequently causes delays in patient care is overcrowding in the emergency room. High patient loads, insufficient personnel, and patient flow bottlenecks are the causes. Better resource allocation, more straightforward procedures, and increased provider collaboration could all be part of the solution.

Aim: To assess the patient's perception of quality regarding the availability of beds and various safety measures to reduce overcrowding in the emergency department. It also aims to assess differences in the quality perception of the measures between the demographic variables like age and gender.

Material and methods: From June 2023 to November 2023, 800 patients in need of emergency care were included in this quantitative, prospective, observational survey study. A quality Likert scale response and a questionnaire were included in this cross-sectional study. The questionnaires' validity and the replies' reliability were assessed in pilot research, including 50 patients. A mixed-mode survey that had written and in-person face-to-face interviews was conducted following approval from the scientific and ethical committee. Nonparametric statistical techniques were used to analyse the data on an ordinal measurement scale.

Results Patients' satisfaction (43%) and dissatisfaction (51%) scores on the availability of beds did not differ significantly. When asked about the outflow measures to reduce crowding in the emergency room, 57% of the patients were unsatisfied, while 9% remained silent. For gender satisfaction for measures to reduce overcrowding, it was discovered that men expressed greater dissatisfaction than women. While 63% of those in the older age group (42–65 years) were unsatisfied with the measures, 60% of the younger age group (18–41 years) were satisfied with the measures. Patients' perceptions of the emergency department's bed availability are roughly identical for both genders (p-value = 0.402) and age (p-value = 0.371); nevertheless, when it comes to the safety measures put in place to reduce overcrowding, the perception of patients is different in gender and age categories (p-value < 0.001).

Conclusion: An ED bed management system can improve patient flow, care coordination, and resource utilisation by providing real-time visibility into patient status and bed availability across all units. Encouraging a favourable patient experience in emergency rooms requires proactive adjustments to reduce overcrowding and continuous monitoring of patient feedback. Ultimately, a

patient-centred approach that combines efficient processes and compassionate care is crucial for achieving higher satisfaction levels despite the challenges posed by overcrowded healthcare settings.

Keywords: Patient satisfaction, overcrowding, emergency department, ordinal data, Nonparametric, Reverse triage

Introduction

Emergency care is the provision of time-sensitive measures that are necessary to prevent death and disability and for which waiting hours can worsen the prognosis or reduce the effectiveness of therapy.¹ The Emergency Department (ED) is one of the most crowded and hectic hospital units, with many patients admitted with high-risk medical and surgical conditions.²

The emergency medical system covers injuries, disorders, obstetrics, and infections that can present acutely. Patients may also present with acute exacerbation of chronic illnesses. Road traffic accidents (RTAs) and other medical emergencies rank among the top causes of death in India. Every year, RTAs alone account for 1.5 lakh fatalities.³ Approximately two people died from heart attacks every hour in 2015–16.⁴ In India, non-communicable diseases have grown to be a severe public health concern, contributing to 53% of all deaths and 62% of the burden of avoided Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs).⁵ About 27% of deaths are related to maternal and neonatal infectious diseases. Pre-hospital and emergency treatment might prevent over 50% of deaths and 40% of the overall disease burden.⁴

When the demand for emergency services exceeds a department's capacity to deliver high-quality care in reasonable timeframes, it is called overcrowding in the emergency department.⁶ A mismatch exists between patient demand and available resources, leading to overwhelming numbers of patients waiting for care and impeding the emergency department's ability to operate. Overcrowding is a result of a variety of factors. Still, it primarily depends on three: the number of patients entering the emergency department (input), the amount of time it takes to process and treat patients (throughput), and the number of patients exiting the facility (output).⁷

Leading causes of overcrowding

Input factors: The factors that cause an increase in ED admissions.^{8,9} Various factors such as unmet care needs, inadequate health education, lack of access to primary healthcare, population growth, ageing of the population, and the rise in seasonal diseases contribute to the increase in hospital admissions. Avoidable accesses, such as frequent non-urgent visits and improper territorial organisational patterns, also play a significant role.¹⁰

Throughput factors: Internal ED factors that impact the length of time from patient admission to hospitalisation, discharge, or transfer (LOS).⁸ Junior physicians in the emergency room and the requirement for specialised consultations are two factors that most affect a patient's length of stay.¹¹ Additional instrumental diagnostic investigations, delays in test results, procedures that are becoming more and more necessary due to comorbidities and ageing, an efficient triage system to ensure appropriate hospitalisations and safe discharges, and a shortage of staff in emergency departments are among the other factors.¹²

Physicians are faced with more patients at once as the number of ED patients rises, which results in information overload for the medical staff. Additionally, when decisions on the dispositions of ED patients are made repeatedly without getting enough rest, their mental resources are exhausted.¹³

Output factors: Hospital overcrowding can occur when patients cannot get beds on time, leading to longer wait times and a negative impact on patient care, boarding, and quality of service. This can happen when a shortage of in-patient beds or transferring patients from the emergency department takes too long. The resulting "exit block" phenomenon can cause doctors to keep patients in the ED, leading to further overcrowding.

The most apparent result of overcrowding in an ED is longer wait times for patients. This, in turn, leads to a rise in the number of patients who leave the ED without seeing a doctor or leaving without being seen (LWBS). Nevertheless, it has been noted that this patient group reports that their conditions are getting worse over time and returns to the hospital soon after (return visit). Because return visits (RVs) might result from treatment or discharge planning failure, early discharge, missed diagnoses, and other factors, RVs are frequently utilised as quality indicators for EDs.¹⁴ Return visits raise medical expenses and resource consumption while delaying patients' proper care.^{14,15} Given that these variables strain available beds, space, and other healthcare resources, it is evident how much they affect overcrowding.⁸

Reducing overcrowding will need several strategies that work in concert, both at the medical (micro level) and administrative (macro level) levels.^{16,8}, is shown schematically in Table 3. Given the diversity of the causes of ED crowding and the need for site-specific solutions, as well as the complexity of emergency departments and the various aspects of overcrowding, a thorough analysis of each ED's unique operation is required to pinpoint the problems, enhance treatment times and patient experiences, and develop strategies to counteract the phenomenon by adjusting input, throughput, or output.

Alongside the advancements in hospital processes, there have been inquiries about healthcare's role in population health and the efficacy of healthcare services. By empowering and involving patients in many parts of their treatment journey, healthcare is changing to become more patient-centric.¹⁷ Research shows involving patients in decision-making leads to better health outcomes. Patient satisfaction studies encourage the engagement of underserved individuals, increase awareness of areas for improvement, and boost patient confidence. This can increase participation and improve healthcare delivery.

Materials and methods

The study was cross-sectional, descriptive, comparative, quantitative, and observational. The study involved patients with Glasgow coma scores of 15 who were admitted to the emergency room, stayed for more than six hours and transferred to inpatient wards. The patients ranged in age from 15 to 65. The study excluded participants with psychiatric disorders and those who had been red-triaged.

Responses were collected by a mixed-mode survey that combined written and in-person interviews with a structured, validated, closed-ended questionnaire. Giving each response a Likert scale score allowed an objective identification of quality perception. Slovin’s sampling formula for 5000 patients following the inclusion criteria, with a 5% margin of error and 95% confidence interval, was 357.

The validity of the questionnaire (coefficient correlation 0.84) and the reliability of the replies (ordinal Omega 0.92) were assessed in pilot research involving 50 patients. Following permission from the Scientific and Ethical Committee, 800 patients were surveyed. IBM SPSS version 29 was used to analyse the data.

Stanley Smith Stevens proposed the four fundamental levels of measurement in 1946: nominal, ordinal, interval, and ratio. The Likert scale is a unidimensional psychometric tool that uses the ordinal categorical scale to represent the strength and intensity of an event, assuming a linear relationship. Likert scale quality items included no comments, very poor, poor, good, and excellent. Respondents who did not respond suggested that they were either unsure of the answer or had no opinion. Descriptive statistics of the sample data were done through bar graphs, pie charts, and frequency distribution tables. The data was found non-normally distributed after the KS and SW tests for normality. The median and mode were considered for the measure of central tendency, and skewness and variance were considered for measures of dispersion from normality. Non-parametric one-sample Wilcoxon sign and Mann-Whitney U tests were used for inferential statistics. Non-parametric tests are more reliable when dealing with data that have unknown or non-normal distributions, which makes them appropriate for ordinal data when the distribution's precise nature may not be apparent. Furthermore, non-parametric tests are less vulnerable to outliers when working with ordinal data with skewed distributions. Parametric tests depend on variables like means and standard deviation and presume a particular distribution of a normal. The best option to prevent bias and inaccuracy is to use nonparametric tests.

Results

1. The availability of beds in the emergency department

Measures to assess the availability of beds in the emergency department.

- i. Reduction in the emergency department's admission wait times
- ii. Treatment delays.
- iii. Faster throughput enables serving more patients.
- iv. Improved admission capacity
- v. Decreased ambulance diversions.

Quality Perception	Score	No. of Respondents		GENDER				AGE					
		n	%	Male		Female		18-41 years		42-65 years			
				n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		

No Comment	1	50	6	23	4.81	27	8.39	25	7.58	25	5.32
Very Poor	2	99	13	61	12.76	38	11.80	45	13.64	75	15.96
Poor	3	301	38	178	37.24	123	38.20	120	36.36	145	31.49
Good	4	203	25	132	27.62	71	22.05	90	27.27	150	31.91
Excellent	5	147	18	84	17.57	63	19.57	25	7.58	25	5.32
TOTAL		800		478		322		330		470	

Table 1: Frequency distribution table for the availability of beds in the emergency department

Figure 1: Pie chart showing percentage

400 out of 800 (50%) patients were unsatisfied when questioned about the number of beds available in the emergency room, 350 out of 800 patients (44%) were satisfied, and 50 patients did not respond.

Figure 2: Bar graph showing comparison

Figure 1: Bar graph showing comparison

response is the primary response for the younger age group with 37%, and good response is the primary response for the older age group with 32%. The distribution is the same for the excellent, around 15%.

Descriptive statistics

- The median response is 3.40 for the grouped data (middle value of the cumulative frequency), which is very close to Poor response, and the Mode is Poor response (3).
- Skewness = -0.236. There is very little negative skewness present. i.e., slightly left-tailed distribution. More values are on the right side of the distribution of responses towards good and excellent.

- **p-value is < 0.001** for K-S and S-W tests (table 4), so the distribution deviates significantly from the normal distribution.

Inferential statistics

One sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test: p-value < 0.001(table 7), which is less than the significant level of 0.05. We reject the null hypothesis. This means the central tendency of the population for the responses towards the availability of beds in the emergency is different from what we assumed to be a Good response. The test is two-sided and statistically significant so that the responses can be both.

Comparison of quality responses for different gender and age groups

Descriptive statistics

- Median for both male and female groups, the younger age group (18-41 years) and the older age group (42-65 years) is 3, i.e., Poor response.
- There is slight negative skewness in the distribution of responses in the male group. (-0.226), female group (-0.230), in the younger age group (-0.255) and the older age group (-0.279).
- p-value < 0.001** for the K-S and S-W tests (table 4). The p-value in both tests is < 0.05, so the distribution deviates significantly from the normal distribution.
- The variance for the male group is 1.139, and the female group's is 1.354. There is a difference in the variance between the two groups. So, for the assumption of homogeneity of variance, we have to look for the shape of the distribution.

Figure 2: Histograms showing shapes of the male groups and the female groups in the population. Variance is homogeneous. So, the **Median** can be taken as the measure of central tendency for comparing the distribution of the responses between the two groups in the population.

- The variance for the younger age group is 1.239, and for the older age group is 1.177. There is a slight difference in the variance between the two groups. So, for the assumption of homogeneity of variance, we have to look for the shape of the distribution.

Looking at the histograms of the male and female groups of patients, the shape of the distribution of responses is almost the same.

p-value = 0.412 (table 5), greater than the significant level of 0.05. So, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. There is no difference in the shapes of the distribution of responses between the male groups and the female groups in the population.

Figure 3: Histograms showing shapes of distribution for age groups

The shape of the histogram of the younger age group and the shape of the histogram of the older age group are almost the same. **p-value = 0.597 (table 6)**, greater than the significant level of 0.05. So, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. There is no difference in the shapes of the distribution of responses between the male groups and the female groups in the population. Variance is homogeneous. So, the **Median** can be taken as

the measure of central tendency for comparing the distribution of the responses between the two groups in the population.

Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test: For the gender comparison, **the p-value = 0.402 (table 7)**, greater than the significant level of 0.05. So, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. The distribution of the Median of the responses for the availability of beds is the same across the male and female categories in the population. For the age group comparison, **the p-value = 0.371 (table 7)** is greater than the significant level of 0.05. So, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. The distribution of the median of the responses for the availability of beds is the same across the population's younger and older age groups.

We can conclude that the perception of bed availability in the emergency department is more or less equal in patients' gender and age categories admitted to the emergency department.

2. Smooth outflow strategies to prevent overcrowding

Outflow measures to reduce overcrowding

- i. Efficient planning measures for admitting patients.
- ii. The discharging process of non-emergent patients.
- iii. Discharge of in-patients before noon by the morning shift.
- iv. Decanting non-emergency lower acuity patients to primary care or outpatient services.
 - i. Weekend in-patient discharge policy. When patients were asked about the abovementioned measures to prevent overcrowding, 57% were unsatisfied, 9% did not comment, and only 34% were satisfied.

Quality Perception	Score	No. of Respondents		GENDER				AGE			
		n	%	Male		Female		18-41 years		42-65 years	
				n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
No Comment	1	72	9	25	5.23	47	14.60	25	7.58	29	6.17
Very Poor	2	192	24	138	28.87	54	16.77	25	7.58	140	29.79
Poor	3	264	33	180	37.66	84	26.09	82	24.85	157	33.40
Good	4	178	22	124	25.94	54	16.77	99	30.00	105	22.34
Excellent	5	94	12	11	2.30	83	25.78	99	30.00	39	8.30
TOTAL		800		478		322		330		470	

Table 2: Frequency distribution table for the smooth outflow measures to prevent overcrowding in the emergency department.

Figure 7: Bar graph showing comparison of gender groups

Figure 6: Pie chart showing percentage distribution

While comparing gender satisfaction responses (figure 7), it was found that males were more dissatisfied than females, with a considerable margin of 20% from females for excellent responses. 60% of the younger age group (18-41 years) are satisfied with the measures taken to reduce overcrowding; on the other hand, 63% of the older age group (42-65 years) are dissatisfied with the measures (figure 8).

Descriptives statistics

- The median for response is 3.02 for the grouped data (middle of the cumulative frequency), and the Mode is Poor (3) response.

- There is also a slightly positive skewness of 0.39. The right-tailed distribution with more values is on the left side of the distribution.
- K-S Test and S-W Test p-value < 0.001. The distribution deviates significantly from the normal distribution. Non-parametric tests were used for inferential statistics.

Inferential statistics

One sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test: We reject the null hypothesis since the **p-value < 0.001**(table 7). This means the central tendency of the population for the responses towards the measures taken to reduce overcrowding in the emergency is different from what we thought to be a Good response.

Comparison of responses for differences in gender and age categories

Descriptive statistics

- The median for both male and female groups is 3, i.e., Poor response. The median in the younger age group (18-41 years) is 4, i.e., good response, and for the older age group (42-65 years), it is 3, i.e., Poor response.
- There is slight negative skewness in the male group (-0.053), and in the female group it is (-0.15). There is negative skewness in the distribution of responses in the younger age group (-0.687), and in the older age group, the distribution is positively skewed, i.e., 0.175.
- K-S and S-W tests for normal distribution: p-value < 0.001 for both tests(table 4). The distribution deviates significantly from the normal distribution. So, Non-parametric tests were used for inferential statistics.

Inferential statistics

- The variance for the male group is 0.843, and the female group's is 1.906. There is a difference in the variance between the two groups. So, for the assumption of homogeneity of variance, we have to look for the shape of the distribution.

Figure 4: Histograms showing shapes of distribution for gender groups

Looking at the histograms of male and female groups of patients, we see that the shapes of the distribution of responses are not the same.

Test for homogeneity of variance: p-value < 0.001(table 5), Which is less than the significant level of 0.05. There is a difference in the shapes of the distribution of responses between the two groups in the population. Variance is heterogeneous. So, we take Mean Ranks to compare the distribution of the responses between the two groups in the population.

responses between the two groups in the population.

- The variance for the younger age group is 1.431, and for the older age group is 1.101. There is a slight difference in the variance between the two groups. So, for the

assumption of homogeneity of variance, we have to look for the shape of the distribution.

Looking at the histograms of the younger and older age groups of patients, we see that the shapes of the distribution of responses are not the same.

Test for homogeneity of variance: p-value = 0.027(table 6), Which is less than the significant level of 0.05. There is no similarity

in the shapes of the distribution of responses between the two age groups in the population.

Figure 5: Histograms showing shapes of

Variance is heterogeneous. So, we take Mean ranks to compare the distribution of the

responses between the two age groups in the population.

Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test

The mean Rank of the male patient group (377.39) is less than the Mean Rank of the female patient group (434.80). The mean Rank of the younger age patient group (484.30) is more than the Mean Rank of the female patient group (341.66).

p-value < 0.001(table 7), Which is much less than the significant level of 0.05. So, we reject the null hypothesis. The distribution of the Mean Ranks of the responses for the measures taken to reduce overcrowding is not the same across the male and female categories and the younger and older age groups in the population.

We can assume that the perception of the quality of the safety measures implemented in the emergency department to reduce overcrowding is different in gender and age categories admitted to the emergency department.

Discussion

Enjoying the highest degree of health is one of everyone's fundamental rights.¹⁸ Regulations by national or state/professional authorities ensure quality assurance for emergency patient treatment and healthcare system management. According to the National Health Profile, just 0.9 beds per 1000 persons are available in India, and only 30% of those beds are in rural regions.¹⁹ This poses a serious problem for rural patients in getting healthcare. Patients turn to dishonest or uninformed providers due to a need for more human resources and diagnostic equipment.¹⁹ Doctors are less likely to practice in rural areas due to poor access to healthcare, housing, education for children, electricity, drinking water, roads, and transportation.²⁰ India will require 20 lakh doctors by 2030, according to the Indian Journal of Public Health.¹³ But still. Presently, a physician at the public hospital treats almost 11,000 patients, above the WHO's recommended ratio of 1:1000.¹³ In addition, there is a deficiency of health service infrastructure in rural areas.²¹

The emergency care system in our country has yet to progress consistently, with some states faring better than others. The government and commercial sectors suffer from fragmented

services, inadequate funding, skilled labour, and controlling laws and rules. The absence of a dedicated academic department and rotating specialists leads to less time devoted to patient care. Consequently, emergency department doctors serve as intermediaries, transporting patients to various specialities. Inexperienced staff often treat the most critical cases.

The INDUS collaboration's white paper on Indian emergency medicine identified several significant problems, including the absence of specialised training in the field.²² According to David et al.²³, two of the three critical components required for the growth of emergency medicine in India were establishing official emergency medicine education and the Medical Council of India's recognition of emergency medicine as a speciality. A much-needed shift occurred in July 2009 when the Medical Council of India designated emergency medicine as the thirty-first speciality in medical training.²⁴

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused challenges for hospital emergency departments, which has led to ED overcrowding. The reasons for this include the large number of frail patients, changes in patient management, and shortage of available beds. Steps must be taken to eliminate exit blocks and reduce crowding to prepare for future pandemics.²⁵

Overcrowding in emergency rooms is a common issue that can harm patients. The quality of medical care is directly lowered in overcrowded emergency departments by factors like longer wait times and higher hospital admission death rates.²⁶ Crowding can result from increased intake, delayed throughput, or diminished output. Indirect issues include lower patient satisfaction and lost revenue for healthcare facilities.^{27,28} Most of the input factors are outside the ED's control.^{8,11} Even if they are not actively involved in the process, they could inadvertently irritate the staff, use medical resources needlessly because of needless hospitalisations, and, as a result, put more strain and hardship on the ED. Stressful situations like these have been shown to lower job satisfaction. Overcrowding is a significant factor in staff reductions.²⁹ Instead of caring for new patients, at least 40% of the medical staff in certain large EDs works with patients who have already had a medical consultation but cannot leave the ED because of exit block and boarding.⁸ It is crucial to assess the impact of overcrowding on the healthcare system and comprehend its numerous origins and effects to create effective solutions.¹⁶

Before looking for answers, it is imperative to evaluate ED crowding accurately and understand its effects based on facts.⁷ To date, there has yet to be an accepted way to measure the various degrees of congestion, but scores are available.³⁰ Scores, such as the Severely Overcrowded and Not-Overcrowded Estimation Tool (SONET), National Emergency Department Overcrowding Score (NEDOCS), and the Community Emergency Department Overcrowding Score (CEDOCS). are available. NEDOCS is a tool that combines several criteria into a score to determine the degree of congestion. A rating of 101 or more indicates overcrowding on a scale ranging from 0 to 200 points.³⁰ Other measuring techniques that may be evaluated to identify overcrowding include the Emergency Department Work Index (EDWIN) score, ED occupancy, ED length of stay, ED volume, ED boarding time, number of boarders, and waiting room number.³¹

Healthcare systems face two main challenges: treatment accessibility and lengthy wait periods. These result in patient dissatisfaction, compromised privacy and confidentiality, and difficulty accessing emergency care due to bed shortages and overcrowding.

Recommendations

Three strategies can be used to tackle overcrowding in the emergency department: restrict emergency visits, increase patient release or transfer, and enhance ED flow.

- i. Only when no patients in the ED are waiting to be admitted are transfers between institutions allowed.³² Ambulances are diverted to presumably less congested hospitals.³³
- ii. According to Huang et al.³⁴, every ED shift should have a clinical assistant. This person would oversee the influx of new patients, hand them off to physicians systematically and effectively, advise them of anticipated wait times, and handle administrative tasks while providing non-medical answers.
- iii. Investing in primary care. Studies by Ansah et al.³⁵ (2019) and Ferreira Amorim et al.³⁶ (2018) suggest that improving primary care can reduce non-emergency visits to the emergency department (ED), thus alleviating ED overcrowding and promoting better health outcomes.
- iv. Families still use emergency departments for elderly or disabled people who would benefit more from long-term care facilities. Partnerships with social care providers can improve discharge.³⁷
- v. Projecting the flow of emergency departments. Using time-series analysis, statistical models can be developed to predict the patient flow in the ED.³⁸
- vi. Increase the bed of internal medicine. Patient flow from the emergency department to internal medicine departments should increase.³⁹
- vii. Provide a real-time resource for patients to learn about wait times. A dashboard that offers current data on ED crowding.⁴⁰ Improve the ED information system.⁴¹
- viii. Observation unit: Link between micro-level and macro-level factors as they are located at the intersection of ED and hospital care.⁴²
- ix. Good triage technique.⁴³ Integration of machine learning with artificial intelligence (AI).⁴⁴ Quick release of stable hospitalised patients is known as "reverse triage."⁴⁵
- x. The access block affects the entire hospital, not just the ED.⁴⁶ "Protocol or action plan for full capacity." Regulatory frameworks and recommended protocols.

Limitation of study

Non parametric test have their strengths but they also come with limitations like assumption of independence, less precision, low sensitivity to the sample size, specially with small sample sizes. To overcome this limitation the sample size was increased to 800 patients. Future studies involving the whole census feedback of the entire population rather than a sample would provide a complete and comprehensive set of data leaving no room for the sampling error. However, when a population is large, diverse or geographically dispersed conducting a complete census ay be impractical or resource-intensive.

Conclusion

Addressing overcrowding in the emergency department requires a multifaceted approach. By implementing measures such as optimised triage systems, increased staffing, streamlined processes, and community education, healthcare facilities can enhance efficiency and provide more timely care. Ongoing assessment through data analytics and a collaborative effort between emergency services and primary care further contribute to long-term solutions. By reducing the difficulties caused by overload, these strategies hope to improve emergency departments' ability to serve patients' needs quickly and effectively.

Overcrowding in the emergency department often negatively impacts patient satisfaction; long wait times, delays in receiving care, and crowded environments contribute to dissatisfaction. To improve patient satisfaction amid overcrowding, healthcare providers should prioritise communication, manage expectations, and actively work on implementing measures to reduce wait times. Transparency about the situation, empathy from the staff, and a commitment to continuous improvement can help mitigate the negative impact of overcrowding on patients' experiences.

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Table 3: Micro-level and macro-level strategies

Strategies	Solutions
Microllevel strategies <i>applied at the level of the Emergency Department</i>	Ensuring priority of hospitalisation of ED patients
	Acceleration of diagnostic pathways
	Fast track
	Availability of specialist consultations

	Outpatient services outside the ED
	Decrease requests for unnecessary advanced diagnostic tests
	Efficient triage strategy
	Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning
Macro level strategies <i>applied at the hospital and/or care system level</i>	Simplifying the admission process
	Smoothing elective admissions
	Early in-patient discharge before 12:00
	Weekend in-patient discharge
	Reducing the number of attendants accompanying a patient
	Optimise staff and resources

Table 4: Tests of Normality

		Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic ^c	df	Sig.
Availability of beds		.194	800	<.001	.902	800	<.001
	Male	.196	478	<.001	.903	478	<.001
	Female	.194	322	<.001	.899	322	<.001
	18-41 Years	.186	330	<.001	.908	330	<.001
	42-65 Years	.195	470	<.001	.908	470	<.001
Outflow measures to reduce Overcrowding		.173	800	<.001	.917	800	<.001
	Male	.197	478	<.001	.891	478	<.001
	Female	.159	322	<.001	.887	322	<.001
	18-41 Years	.208	330	<.001	.866	330	<.001
	42-65 Years	.181	470	<.001	.909	470	<.001
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction							

Table 5: Test of Homogeneity of Variance for Gender

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Availability of beds	Based on Mean	1.915	1	798	.167
	Based on Median	.673	1	798	.412
	Based on the Median and with adjusted df	.673	1	794.869	.412
	Based on trimmed mean	2.079	1	798	.150
Outflow measures to	Based on Mean	98.067	1	798	<.001
	Based on Median	79.679	1	798	<.001

reduce Overcrowding	Based on the Median and with adjusted df	79.679	1	735.016	<.001
	Based on trimmed mean	101.884	1	798	<.001

Table 6: Test of Homogeneity of Variance for Age Groups

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
<i>Availability of beds</i>	Based on Mean	.009	1	798	.925
	Based on Median	.280	1	798	.597
	Based on the Median and with adjusted df	.280	1	795.306	.597
	Based on trimmed mean	.001	1	798	.973
<i>Outflow measures to reduce Overcrowding</i>	Based on Mean	13.393	1	798	<.001
	Based on Median	4.890	1	798	.027
	Based on the Median and with adjusted df	4.890	1	763.833	.027
	Based on trimmed mean	10.705	1	798	.001

Table 7: Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig. ^{a,b}	Decision
1	The median of Availability of beds equals 4.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	<.001	Reject the null hypothesis.
2	The median of outflow measures to reduce Overcrowding equals 4.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	<.001	Reject the null hypothesis.
3	The distribution of Availability of beds is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.402	Retain the null hypothesis.
4	The distribution of outflow measures to reduce Overcrowding is the same across categories of Gender.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	<.001	Reject the null hypothesis.
5	The distribution of availability of beds is the same across age categories.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.371	Retain the null hypothesis.

6	The distribution of outflow measures to reduce Overcrowding is the same across categories of Age.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	<.001	Reject the null hypothesis.
a. The significance level is .050.				
b. Asymptotic significance is displayed.				